

Artificial Intelligence in Endodontics (Part III)

Dr. Rajiv K. Chugh

President Elect, Indian Dental Association (H.O.)

Member, Dental Council of India

Secretary General, Indian Academy of Restorative Dentistry

Editor-in-Chief (Asia), UPDENT- A Journal of Advanced Dentistry

Senate Member, Pierre Fauchard Academy, India Section

Other dental applications of AI

In Dental Education

AI is frequently employed in the field of dental education to generate situations that simulate clinical work on patients and minimize all the hazards involved with training on a live patients. This has significantly improved the preclinical virtual patient feedback to the students. It has been observed that the effectiveness of these systems have shown that students develop a competency-based skill level more quickly with these systems than with conventional simulator units.

For Patient Management

Virtual dental assistants powered by artificial intelligence can carry out several duties in the dental office with more accuracy and fewer mistakes, and it requires less manpower for their functioning than an actual human. It can help with clinical diagnosis, treatment planning, scheduling appointments and many more tasks. It is highly helpful in informing the dentist about the patient's medical history and any habits they may have, such as smoking and drinking.

For Diagnosis, Treatment, and Prognosis

The application of artificial intelligence in the diagnosis and treatment of diseases of the oral soft tissue as well as in the detection and classification of suspiciously changed mucosa experiencing premalignant and malignant alterations can be beneficial. Even little changes at the single-pixel level that the human eye could miss are detected. Artificial intelligence may be able to correctly identify a large population's genetic propensity for oral cancer. A useful tool for determining dental prognosis in light of the treatment strategy is an AI-based machine learning system. AI has been found to determine a tooth's long-term prognosis for oral health and function, and plan a thorough treatment strategy.

In Dental Radiology

AI is being effectively utilized in dental radiology for various diagnostic procedures in terms of digital RVGS/IOPA, 3D scans, and CBCT. It can help to create an AI that would aid in quick diagnosis and treatment planning.

In Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery

The biggest use of artificial intelligence has been in oral and maxillofacial surgery. Surgery has undergone a revolutionary change thanks to AI, it has been utilized in the development of robotic surgery in which the human body motion and intellect are replicated. The image-guided surgeries are performed for dental implant surgery procedures, removal of tumours and foreign objects, biopsies and temporomandibular joint (TMJ) surgery and many more cranial surgical procedures that have been successful in clinical settings. Various studies of oral implant surgery have demonstrated significantly improved accuracy when compared to the freehand procedure, even when performed by competent surgeons. All these have shown lesser operation time, higher intraoperative accuracy, and safer manipulation around delicate structures.

In Prosthetic Dentistry

Laboratories are utilizing AI to autonomously create innovative dental restorations that meet the highest standards for fit, function, and aesthetics. This will benefit dentistry, but it will also have a significant influence on orofacial and craniofacial prosthetics.

In Orthodontics

Orthodontic diagnosis, planning, and treatment monitoring are now all possible using AI. Analysis of radiographs and images taken by intraoral scanners and cameras can be used for diagnosis and treatment planning. This has helped producing patient impressions, and the

findings are often far more precise than human perception. Utilizing a unique treatment strategy, accurate 3D scans and virtual models, it is simple to 3D print the aligners. The Artificial Intelligence-assisted aligners promise to shorten treatment times and simplify appointment schedules in addition to providing accurate treatment execution and progress monitoring.

In Forensic Odontology

AI has been extensively applied in forensic medicine. It has shown to be quite effective in determining the biological age and gender of the healthy and ill person. Additionally, it is employed for analyzing bite marks and predicting mandibular morphology.

Dentistry is set to benefit from some of the most fascinating uses of AI. The dental chair, a crucial component of the dental practice, saw a significant shift from physiologic, hydraulic pressure chairs, with a manual pump to become electric with attached multiple sensors. The most recent innovation is a voice-command dental chair that doesn't require the doctor to physically do anything.

Last but not the least, one of the most creative uses of AI is in the field of "bioprinting," which allows living tissue and even organs to be created in successive thin layers of cells and may one day be used to reconstruct oral hard and soft tissues that have been lost due to pathological or unintentional causes.

Impact of artificial intelligence on dentists

Although there is plenty of talk about how AI can change dentistry, questions remain about whether it will ever completely replace dentists. Thankfully, dentistry performed by machines and without human interaction does not represent clinical care. Machines cannot provide clinical intuition, intangible perception, or empathy, which are essential to providing individualized healthcare and professionalism. The most fascinating aspect of human-to-human communication cannot be easily translated into computer language.